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Research Article

**COMPARATIVE EFFECT OF FIXED DOSE COMBINATION
OF BISOPROLOL+ AMLODIPINE VERSUS BISOPROLOL
AND AMLODIPINE ALONE ON BLOOD PRESSURE IN
STAGE-2 ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS**Dr. Muhammad Mashood¹, Dr. Maryam Shabbir², Dr. Zahoor Ahmed Khan³¹ BHU 297 HR Tehsil Fort Abbas Distt Bahawalnagar² PGT Abbas Institute of Medical Sciences MZD AJK³ MO at BHU. 212/9.R Tehsil Fort Abbas Distt Bahawalnagar**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Employment of low dose combinations of two antihypertensives, with different mode of action has gained acceptance worldwide for the treatment of mild to moderate hypertension. However, most studies in hypertensive disease have focused on monotherapy. The combination therapy in the treatment of hypertension is largely extrapolated from these monotherapy studies.

Objectives: To study and compare the effect of amlodipine, bisoprolol and fixed dose combination of amlodipine + bisoprolol on blood pressure in stage-2 essential hypertensive patients.

Methods: The present study was carried out in Department of Pharmacology in collaboration with Department of Medicine at Mayo Hospital, Lahore for six months duration from October 2019 to March 2020.

Results and Conclusion: Amlodipine + bisoprolol in fixed dose combination have showed significant blood pressure control in patients of stage-2 essential hypertension and the antihypertensive effect was greater than individual monotherapy study groups.

Keywords: Amlodipine, Bisoprolol, Hypertension stage 2.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension is a public health problem affecting millions of people in most countries (more than 50 million in India) and causes early death and brain trauma, heart failure, kidney failure and myocardial infarction if not properly treated. The purpose of hypertension is to detect and control high blood pressure in people affected by the disease¹⁻². Modern antihypertensive pharmacological therapy can effectively reduce the risk of morbidity and mortality due to high blood pressure, and thus coronary artery, cerebral and kidney diseases. The traditional approach to treating advocates is one measure, followed by a low dose of value if needed. However, monotherapy is effective only in 50-60% of cases, because many mechanisms play a role in the pathogenesis of spontaneous hypertension, and one class of drugs can not interfere with all defective pathways. In addition, it is more likely to stimulate compensatory mechanisms that cause side effects and partially reduce incremental gain, as drugs are administered at higher doses³⁻⁴. Pharmacological treatment of hypertension, as with any pharmacological intervention, is aimed at achieving the desired therapeutic response without producing toxicity, maximizing its effectiveness and minimizing unpleasant side effects. Combinations of drugs that emphasize the "amazing care" approach are typically developed for individuals who contain full doses of the strength of each agent and do not respond independently to hypertension. A single pharmacological treatment, even if it is evaluated maximum, only modest hypertension in stage 1 or 2 in the best condition is effective in normalizing blood pressure, which accounts for the majority of the hypertensive population⁵⁻⁶. It is increasingly appreciated that the difficult blood pressure target "normal" is achieved only when multi-drug therapy is used⁷⁻⁸. Treatment options for many drugs are quite simple, either the combination therapy of a fixed dose or drugs added one by one, and then come up with an effective regimen of many drugs. The use of two combinations of antihypertensive drugs in small doses has gained worldwide acceptance in the treatment of mild to moderate hypertension with different types of action⁹⁻¹⁰. The same JNC-VI and JNC-VII reports confirmed the promise that when blood pressure is higher than 20/10 mm Hg above the target, separate prescriptions or fixed dose combinations should be agreed to start with two medications. Since the two drugs are useful for a disorder used separately, it does not necessarily mean that their combination is equally effective or more useful. However, most studies on hypertensive diseases focus on monotherapy¹¹⁻¹². Combination therapy for the treatment of hypertension is largely extrapolated from these monotherapy studies. Several studies directly compared different classes of

antihypertensive drugs in terms of their effectiveness, safety and quality of life, but very few experiments compare combination therapy in small doses with standard dose alone. In this study, combination therapy in low doses, an effective and rational alternative to the first treatment of hypertension compared to traditional monotherapy, was evaluated in the necessary patients with hypertension in phase 2, a combination amlodipine + bisoprolol and ammonia + bisoprolol fixed doses of bisoprolol.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The present study was carried out in Department of Pharmacology in collaboration with Department of Medicine at Mayo Hospital, Lahore for six months duration from October 2019 to March 2020. The study enrolled 60 patients (n=60) of both sexes who went to the clinic and were diagnosed with hypertension and second-degree hypertension that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Study design: Open parallel, comparative, randomized, controlled, prospective study

Inclusion criteria: Patients with clinically proven stage II essential hypertension defined as systolic blood pressure ≥ 160 mm Hg and diastolic blood pressure ≥ 100 mm Hg (based on an average of two or more readings at each of two or more visits) according to the JNC- VII aged 40-65 years and willing to give informed consent were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Patients with angina requiring drug therapy with nitrates, beta-blockers, calcium channel blockers, or dipyridamole, or receiving other antihypertensive drugs. Patient with a history of myocardial infarction, percutaneous coronary angioplasty (PTCA), coronary artery bypass graft (CABG), cerebrovascular accident (CVA), type -1 diabetes, or transient ischemic attack (TIA). Patient with severe hematological (SGPT more than 50% above the upper limit of normal), metabolic, gastrointestinal or endocrine abnormalities. Patient with serum creatinine greater than 2.5 mg / dl or creatinine clearance less than 50 ml / min, if available. Patient with known hypersensitivity to amlodipine or bisoprolol. Pregnant and lactating women of childbearing age who do not use effective contraception. Participation in similar surveys during the last year.

Procedure: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee. Patients were thoroughly explained the study design and risks, and informed written consent was obtained from patients. The participants had all basic tests, such as complete blood count, liver function tests, kidney function

tests, blood sugar, fundus, ECG, total cholesterol (mg / dL), serum creatinine (mg / dL), SGPT (i .l). The above studies were performed at the beginning and end of the study. Eligible patients were divided into three groups of twenty each using a computer-generated randomization table in a block of ten (calculated from True Epistat, Standard Edition 1999).

Research groups: Group 1: amlodipine 5 mg once a day, Group 2: bisoprolol 5 mg once a day, Group 3: 5 mg amlodipine + bisoprolol once a day. All the above-mentioned drugs are given to patients for a month's therapy. Concomitant treatment: Concomitant use of antihypertensive medications was not allowed during the study. Patients taking any concomitant medications were registered.

Observation: Each patient in the appropriate group received free samples for seven days and was asked to visit (control) to measure blood pressure. At each visit, patients were assessed for blood pressure control (the patient was said to be in blood pressure control when blood pressure had reached a target of $\leq 140/90$ mmHg), and asked about their history of adverse drug reactions. All patients were advised about diet and exercise. Drug replenishment took place at each visit. Each patient was assessed over a period of one month, after which all studies were repeated for comparison. Efficacy was assessed by blood pressure control during the study. Tolerance was assessed by noting any adverse drug events during the study.

Blood pressure measurement: At least two measurements were taken on two or more separate occasions before the patient was marked as hypertensive. The American Heart Association recommends two readings with an interval of at least 30 seconds and an average of the two readings.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using a paired "t" test to compare the effects of amlodipine, bisoprolol, and the combination on blood pressure during therapy. An unpaired "t" test was used for comparison between the groups after treatment.

RESULTS:

Patients (n = 60) with stage II essential hypertension completed the study. As shown in Table 1 for Group I patients, the mean systolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from Visit 1 to Visit 3 (160.7 ± 13.61 to 153.6 ± 9.65 mm Hg), and Mean diastolic blood pressure also decreased after the 2nd week, i.e. from Visit -1 to Visit-3 (103.4 ± 3.25 to 101.2 ± 4.02 mm Hg), which was not statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). mean systolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from visit 3 to 5 (153.6 ± 9.65 to 134 ± 4.81 mmHg), and mean diastolic blood pressure also decreased after 2 weeks. weeks, i.e. from Visit 3 to Visit-5 (101.2 ± 4.02 to 86.6 ± 2.83 mmHg), which was highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$ **). 80% of patients in group I required the addition of bisoprolol to control blood pressure.

Table.1: Comparative effect on blood pressure in group-1 (Amlodipine 5mg OD)

Blood Pressure (mm Hg)	Mean Value Visit-1	Mean Value Visit-2	Mean Value Visit-3	'P'- Value	Mean Value Visit-3	Mean Value Visit-4	Mean Value Visit-5	'P'- Value
Systolic	160.7 $\pm$ 3.6	154.7 $\pm$ 8.0	153.6 $\pm$ 9.6	<0.05	153.6 $\pm$ 9.6	137.2 $\pm$ 5.0	134 $\pm$ 4.81**	<0.001
Diastolic	103.4 $\pm$ 3.2	99.3 $\pm$ 2.8	101.2 $\pm$ 4.0	<0.05	101.2 $\pm$ 4.0	86.7 $\pm$ 2.8	86.6 $\pm$ 2.83**	<0.001

As shown in Table 2, the mean systolic blood pressure in Group II patients decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from Visit 1 to Visit 3 (164.1 ± 4.17 to 161.9 ± 6.72 mmHg), and mean diastolic blood pressure decreased after 2–weeks, i.e. from Visit-1 to Visit-3 (105.3 ± 5.03 to 103.5 ± 3.83 mm Hg), which was not statistically significant ($p < 0, 05$).

Table.2: comparative effect on blood pressure in group-2 (Bisoprolol 5mg OD)

Blood Pressure (mm Hg)	Mean Value Visit-1	Mean Value Visit-2	Mean Value Visit-3	'P'- Value	Mean Value Visit-3	Mean Value Visit-4	Mean Value Visit-5	'P'- Value
Systolic	164.1 $\pm$ 4.1	159.4 $\pm$ 8.6	161.9 $\pm$ 6.7	<0.05	161.9 $\pm$ 6.7	138.8 $\pm$ 4.6	135.2 $\pm$ 2.7**	<0.001
Diastolic	105.3$\pm$5.0	101.8$\pm$5.3	103.5$\pm$3.8	<0.05	103.5$\pm$ 3.8	89.5$\pm$3.03	86.5$\pm$2.03**	<0.001

In patients not responding to bisoprolol 5 mg alone, with the addition of amlodipine 5 mg, mean systolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from Visit III to Visit 5 (161.9 ± 6.72 to 135.2 ± 2.70 mmHg) and mean

diastolic blood pressure also decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from visit-3 to visit-5 (103.5 ± 3.83 to $86.5^{**} \pm 2.03$ mm Hg), which was highly statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In patients not responding to bisoprolol 5 mg alone, with the addition of amlodipine 5 mg, mean systolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from Visit III to Visit 5 (161.9 ± 6.72 to $135.2^{**} \pm 2.70$ mmHg) and mean diastolic blood pressure also decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from visit-3 to visit-5 (103.5 ± 3.83 to $86.5^{**} \pm 2.03$ mm Hg), which was highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). 90% of patients required the addition of amlodipine to control blood pressure.

Table-3: Comparative effect on blood pressure in group-3 (Amlodipine + Bisoprolol)

Blood Pressure (mm Hg)	Mean Value Visit-1	Mean Value Visit-2	Mean Value Visit-3	'P'-Value	Mean Value Visit-3	Mean Value Visit-4	Mean Value Visit-5	'P'-Value
Systolic	164.2±4.6	147.5±9.5	140.8±9.3**	<0.001	140.8±9.3	136.2± 10.2	136.0±8.4*	<0.05
Diastolic	104.6± 3.8	94.8±6.3	88.2±4.3**	<0.001	88.2± 4.3	87.6±3.7	86.9± 4.0*	<0.05

As shown in Table 3, for patients in Group III, mean systolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. From Visit 1 to Visit 3 (164.2 ± 4.62 to $140.8^{**} \pm 9.34$ mm Hg) and mean diastolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from Visit 1 to Visit 3 (104.6 ± 3.89 to $88.2^{**} \pm 4.39$ mm Hg), which was highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Mean systolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks, i.e. from Visit 3 to Visit 5 (140.8 ± 9.34 to $136.0^{*} \pm 8.48$ mm Hg), and mean diastolic blood pressure decreased after 2 weeks ie from visit 3rd to visit. 5 (88.2 ± 4.39 to $86.9^{*} \pm 4.07$ mm Hg), which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Visit 3: There was no significant difference in mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure in Group I and Group II ($p < 0.05$).

Table- 4: Comparative effects on systolic blood pressure in all study groups (Mean ± SD)

Follow up	Mean Values of Systolic Blood Pressure (mm Hg)		
	GROUP-1	GROUP-2	GROUP-3
VISIT-1	160.7 ± 13.61	164.1 ± 4.17	164.2 ± 4.62
VISIT-2	154.7 ± 8.06	159.4 ± 8.63	147.5 ± 9.51
VISIT-3	153.6± 9.65	161.9 ± 6.72	140.8 ± 9.34
VISIT-4	137.2 ± 5.04	138.8 ± 4.69	136.2± 10.25
VISIT-5	134.0 ± 4.81	135.2 ± 2.70	136.0 ± 8.48

There was a decrease in mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure in group III compared to group I and group II, which was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Visit-5: No significant difference in mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure was noted in all study groups ($p < 0.05$).

Table.5: Comparative effects on diastolic blood pressure in all study groups (Mean ± SD)

Follow up	Mean Values of Diastolic Blood Pressure (mm Hg)		
	GROUP-1	GROUP-2	GROUP-3
VISIT-1	103.4 ± 3.25	105.3 ± 5.03	104.6 ± 3.89
VISIT-2	99.3 ± 2.84	101.8 ± 5.34	94.8 ± 6.30
VISIT-3	101.2 ± 4.02	103.5 ± 3.83	88.2 ± 4.39
VISIT-4	86.7 ± 2.84	89.5 ± 3.03	87.6 ± 3.70
VISIT-5	86.6 ± 2.83	86.5 ± 2.03	86.9 ± 4.07

DISCUSSION:

An important rationale for low dose therapy of two agents is to reduce dose-related side effects while achieving similar or better pressure control than with full doses of either agent. To reduce side effects and improve blood pressure control, combination therapy has been widely accepted but has not been adequately tested¹¹. The present study

also showed a similarly stronger antihypertensive effect when bisoprolol was added in group I and amlodipine was added in group II compared to monotherapy in the respective groups. L Weiner and G. Frithz reported that bisoprolol appears to be an effective antihypertensive agent in mild to moderate hypertension; The present study does not support the claim as the addition of amlodipine was

required to control blood pressure in group II. The results of this study were consistent with studies by Lewin A J, Lueg M C et al. 1993 Unzueta Montoy A et al., 2003 Prisant L M, 2002; Frishman W. H et al., 1995; as the combination of amlodipine 5 mg + bisoprolol 5 mg showed a statistically significant reduction in systolic and diastolic blood pressure and no change in heart rate ($p < 0.05$)¹². There were also no clinically significant changes in laboratory parameters since the baseline visit. Prisant L M et al. 1998; The study showed that the mean change in systolic and diastolic blood pressure from baseline for placebo (n = 79) was -0.1 / -2.2 mmHg, amlodipine (n = 154) -12.4 / -10, 3 mm Hg, enalapril (n = 155) -9.4 / -8.2 mm Hg and bisoprolol / hydrochlorothiazide (n = 155) -14.0 / -12.0 mm Hg. The overall efficacy analysis showed a statistically significant reduction in sitting diastolic blood pressure for 10 mg bisoprolol + 6.25 mg hydrochlorothiazide compared with placebo, amlodipine and enalapril¹³⁻¹⁴. There was a significant reduction in seated systolic blood pressure for 10 mg bisoprolol + 6.25 mg hydrochlorothiazide compared with placebo plus enalapril but not with amlodipine. There was also a significant drop in heart rate while sitting for 10 mg bisoprolol + 6.25 mg hydrochlorothiazide (-6.2 bpm) compared to placebo (+0.1 bpm), amlodipine (+1.2 bpm) and enalapril (+0.5 beats / min) / min).¹⁸ Our study results showed similar responses, but at a low dose of 5 mg amlodipine and 5 mg bisoprolol. While the present study does not support the claim of Papademetriou V et al. 1998; who reported that the efficacy of the low-dose combination of bisoprolol and hydrochlorothiazide with amlodipine and enalapril was at least as effective as amlodipine and more effective than enalapril in both men and women¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

Amlodipine + bisoprolol in fixed dose combination have showed significant blood pressure control in patients of stage-2 essential hypertension and the antihypertensive effect was greater than individual monotherapy study groups. As this combination has shown excellent response in low doses, this combination can be considered as an alternative to existing strategies in combination therapies for the management of stage-2 essential hypertension

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